

manure. and an effective nitrification inhibitor.

To verify these attributes of neem products, field trials conducted at Mbita Point Field Station of ICIPE in western Kenya used neem oil, neem cake, and blended urea-neem cake. Urea-neem cake is a mixture of 1,000 g urea fertilizer (46% N) to 250 g neem cake. Neem cake and urea-neem cake were incorporated in the subsoil at land preparation before transplanting at similar neem cake rates. Neem oil was sprayed on rice plants 1, 30, and 55 days after transplanting (DT). It was mixed with water and sprayed at 6, 15, and 30% emulsified concentration (EC), the equivalent of 10, 25, and 50 liters/ha, respectively. Sindano, a traditional rice variety, was grown without additional fertilizer.

During the trial, the predominant insect species were the white borer *Maliarpha separatella* and the pink borer *Sesamia calamistis*. *M. separatella* caused a large proportion of unfilled grains. *S. calamistis* caused whiteheads at plant maturity. The stalk-eyed fly *Diopsis thoracica* and *D. apicalis* infested rice at early vegetative phase and caused deadhearts.

Neem oil at high concentrations was better protection than neem cake or urea-neem cake at early vegetative stage. Plots treated with urea-neem cake had more deadhearts than those treated with neem cake, which showed that N induced

Effect of neem products on stem borer infestation and rice yield in western Kenya.^a

Treatment	Rate/ha	Insect infestation ^b			Yield components						
		Deadhearts (%)	Whiteheads (no./1000 tillers)	Stem infestation (%)	Harvest index ^c	Weight of filled grains per hill (g)					
Neem oil	10 liters	3.1	cd	.3	b	60	ab	42.1	a	31.9	ab
	25 -	2.0	de	.6	b	53	ab	42.8	ab	31.5	ab
	50 -	0.0	f	.8	b	51	ab	42.8	ab	38.8	b
Neem cake (NC)	10 kg	1.9	e	.5	b	49	b	42.8	ab	27.7	ab
	25 -	1.4	e	.5	b	49	b	43.5	b	44.2	bc
	50 -	2.8	d	.2	b	37	c	43.8	b	52.5	c
Urea-neem cake	50 - (10 kg NC + 40 kg urea)	4.4	b	.3	b	37	c	44.4	bc	35.3	b
Blended urea-neem cake mixture	125 - (25+100-)	3.5	c	1.1	ab	43	b	44.8	c	52.5	c
	250 - (50+200-)	2.6	d	.7	b	37	c	44.7	c	62.4	d
Untreated	0	8.5	a	4.5	a	69	a	41.5	a	21.6	a

^aMean of 3 replications of 12-m² plots each. Means in a column followed by common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDeadhearts: percent tillers with deadhearts at 60 DT, caused mainly by *Diopsis* spp. Whiteheads: number of whiteheads in 1,000 tillers at harvest; stem infestation: percent stem infested by *M. separatella*.

^cHarvest index = $\frac{\text{dry grain weight}}{\text{dry grain and straw weight}} \times 100$

Diopsis infestation and attenuated the systemic effect of neem cake (see table).

At harvest, percentage stem infestation of *M. separatella* was significantly lower in plots treated with neem cake and urea-neem cake than in untreated and neem-oil-treated plots. However, there was no significant difference in the number of whiteheads. Neem oil does not affect *M. separatella* infestation, probably because it has low persistence under sunshine and high temperature.

Crops treated with neem cake and

urea-neem cake had higher grain and straw weights than plots treated with low concentrations of neem oil and untreated plots. Results showed that combining neem cake and nitrogen fertilizer produces significantly higher yields. When rice stems were dissected at harvest, high larval mortality and delayed *M. separatella* development were observed in plots where neem cake or urea-neem cake was applied. The systemic effect of neem cake might be related to *M. separatella* mortality and low stem infestation.

Parasitization of gall midge maggots in exposed and suppressed galls

N. C. Patnaik and J. M. Sathpathy, Entomology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, India

Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* infestation causes galls, often called silvershoots. Infested plants compensate by producing excessive tillers that give the rice plant a bushy look. These tillers are unproductive and galls forming within them do not protrude through the leaf whorl, but harbor maggots parasitized by *Platygaster oryzae* (Cameron), an egg-larval parasite.

Rice workers scoring for varietal

1. Exposed and suppressed galls in Jaya, Bhubaneswar, India.

resistance or susceptibility to gall midge or recording midge infestation and parasitization in the field often do not record infestation and parasitization of suppressed galls.

To estimate the proportion of exposed and suppressed galls in the infested hills, 20 random hills of Jaya in the vegetative stage were dissected every 2 weeks for 3 years and 7,541 galls were tested to determine the parasitization percentage in exposed versus suppressed galls.

There was a 4:1 ratio of exposed to suppressed galls (Fig. 1). Parasitization in the suppressed galls was higher during early Apr, May, and Jun, late Jan and Mar, and in Jul (Fig. 2). □

2. Parasitization of galls by *Platygaster oryzae*.

Thaia subrufa (Homoptera:Cicadellidae) occurrence in Karnataka, India

Gavi Gowda, K. R. Jayaram, and Nagaraju, Regional Research Station, University of Agricultural Sciences, Mudigere - 577132, Karnataka, India

Thaia leafhoppers are becoming serious pests of cereals, especially rice. *Thaia oryzivora* Ghauri and *T. subrufa* (Motschulsky) cause substantial damage to rice in several Asian countries.

In Feb 1978, *T. subrufa* adults and nymphs were found in large numbers on leaf blades of rice seedlings in summer crop nurseries in Mudigere. Infestation persisted, even on transplanted rice plants, in Mar-Apr 1978 and caused hopperburn symptoms in some plots. Panicle size in affected plots was considerably reduced. Leafhopper populations were so high that 150 to 200 adults were col-

lected in each sweep of a 25-cm diameter insect net. The ratio of males to females ranged from 1:1.20 to 1:2.06 in different months.

Adults and nymphs usually sucked on the leaf undersurface, causing white specks on the upper surface, which often ran into zigzag lines. The specks later turned brown and gave the plants a burnt appearance. When enclosed on rice plants in the laboratory, a single adult damaged a 1-cm² area a day. Preliminary biological observations show that the nymphal period lasts 23-25 days and has 5 instars, and that adults live 33-45 days.

Pest activity in the rice fields has been monitored since 1978. Although found throughout the year, the pest bred actively Oct-May and severely damaged the summer crop. Light trap catches of adults are shown in the table. The pest was also seen on several grass weeds and on finger millet *Eleusine coracana* Gaertn.

Light trap catches of *Thaia subrufa* in Karnataka, India.

Month	Leafhoppers (no.) ^a	
	1981	1982
Jan	577	205
Feb	635	145
Mar	287	59
Apr	175	231
May	92	168
Jun	4	2
Jul	0	2
Aug	-	-
Sep	0	-
Oct	16	3
Nov	164	193
Dec	246	99

^a - = no observation.

Dimethoate, methyl parathion, and quinalphos at 0.05% spray effectively controlled the pest. Leafhopper populations also declined after a heavy rain. □

Effect of nitrogen and plant density on rice stem borer infestation in Western Kenya

D. T. Ho, entomologist, and J. G. Kibuka, technician, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, P.O. Box 30772, Nairobi, Kenya

A survey of rice ecosystems in Kenya showed that rice farmers grow rice in low-fertility swamps at high plant density (about 1 million hills/ha at 10- × 10-cm

spacing) because they believe higher plant populations will produce higher yields.

We studied the effect of plant density and fertility on insect infestation in field trials at Mbita Point, in western Kenya, under swampy lowland conditions. Sindano, a traditional rice variety, was grown on black cotton soil (saline phase, gleyic solonetz) composed of 40% sand, 14% silt, and 46% clay. Rice was planted at 10- × 20- and 20- × 20-cm spacing for populations of 500,000 and 250,000 hills/ha. Nitrogen was applied at

0,60, and 120 kg/ha at land preparation with 30 kg P and 50 kg K/ha. The predominant rice insect was stem borer. No disease was observed.

Results showed that stem borer damage was the same for crops at different plant densities, except at 120 kg N/ha. Deadhearts were caused by *Diopsis* spp. and whiteheads by *Sesamia calamistis*.

Infestation by combined *S. calamistis* and *Maliarpha separattella* did not differ among treatments (see table), but percentage of empty grains was significant.